

15
14
13
12
11
10
9
8
7
6
5
4
3
2
1
All

0.00

0.05

0.10

0.15

MR leave-one-out sensitivity analysis for triglycerides on Sensorineural hearing loss

-0.15

-0.10

-0.05

0.00

MR leave-one-out sensitivity analysis for HDL cholesterol on Sensorineural hearing loss

All

-0.05

0.00

0.05

MR leave-one-out sensitivity analysis for apolipoprotein B on Sensorineural hearing loss

